

INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS FOR ACCOUNTING FOR INVESTMENTS.

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Abstract. The article offers a new method of factor analysis of consolidated financial statements, developed by the author on the basis of a detailed study of the features of the use of consolidation techniques. Special attention is paid to the analysis of the influence of various factors on the value of the currency of the consolidated balance sheet.

Keywords: type of integration, factor analysis, participation rate, goodwill, non-controlling interest, coefficient, consolidation, elimination.

Introduction. There have been significant changes in IFRS with respect to standards related to the consolidation of financial statements. Thus, the International Financial Reporting Standard (IAS) 27 "Consolidated and Separate Financial Statements" as amended in 2008 was discontinued. and instead of it, two standards were adopted - the International Financial Reporting Standard (IAS) 27 "Separate Financial Statements" and the International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) 10 "Consolidated Financial Statements", replacing the requirements of the old standard IFRS (IAS) 27 and PKI-12 "Consolidation-Special Purpose Enterprises".

The purpose of IAS 27 is to establish accounting and disclosure rules for investments. With the advent of the new IFRS 10, IAS 27 has acquired a concise form and began to contain definitions of only two concepts: "consolidated financial statements" and "separate financial statements". The remaining definitions relating to the types of control, parent company, subsidiary, joint venture, etc., have been

transferred to IFRS 10. The basic rules of consolidation and complex issues related to the emergence of control are now also addressed in IFRS 10.

In the new IAS 27, consolidated financial statements are defined as the financial statements of the group, in which the assets, liabilities, equity, income, expenses and cash flows of the parent company and its subsidiaries are presented as the financial statements of a single economic entity [3].

Separate financial statements in accordance with IAS 27 are statements prepared by the parent company or an investor exercising joint control over the investment object. Separate financial statements are presented in addition to the CFR, in which investments are accounted for using the equity method. At the same time, it should be noted that the financial statements prepared using the equity method are not separate financial statements.

An entity should recognize dividends received from a subsidiary, joint venture or associate as part of profit or loss in its separate financial statements at the time when the entity's right to receive dividends is established.

When establishing a new enterprise as a parent enterprise, the requirements must be met that the new parent enterprise acquires control of the original parent enterprise by issuing equity instruments in exchange for existing equity instruments. The assets and liabilities of the new group and the original group do not change after the reorganization; the new parent company must measure the cost at the date of reorganization at the book value of its share.

This standard came into force on January 1, 2013.

The capital consolidation technique is based on the fact that the book value of the parent company's investments in each subsidiary, as well as the parent company's share in the capital of each subsidiary should be mutually excluded. Previously, in

IAS 27 as amended in 2003, " mutual exclusion "was called" elimination", the purpose of which is to eliminate the double counting of those transactions that will be shown twice in the financial statements when summing up.

Investments of the parent company in a subsidiary can be 100%, or they can be equity.

With 100 % participation of the parent company in the authorized capital of the subsidiary, the active article of the parent company "Investments in subsidiaries" and the passive article of the subsidiary "Authorized capital" are completely mutually exclusive.

When consolidating capital with equity participation, the participation coefficient is determined, it is multiplied by the amount of the authorized capital of the subsidiary, and the resulting amount of capital is mutually excluded.

The development of international trade, the emergence of multinational companies, the globalization of the capital market, the globalization of economic processes and information technologies caused the need to harmonize the financial statements of companies in different countries. In recent years, the processes of harmonization of accounting for financial statements at the international level have significantly accelerated. Interest in the introduction and application of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) is actively growing in Uzbekistan. This is one of the most important factors for improving the efficiency of corporate governance, investment attractiveness, competitiveness and ensuring business transparency. We should not ignore, of course, the Covid-19 pandemic. In recent months, in connection with the coronavirus pandemic, many governments have taken restrictive measures that have somehow affected the activities of all enterprises and their financial statements. In this research paper, we will try to consider the most

significant consequences of the pandemic for the preparation of financial statements based on the current IFRS rules.

On February 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the resolution " On additional measures for the transition to international Financial Reporting Standards " No. PP-4611, which opens a new page in the history of the transition to IFRS in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The adopted document provides for a radical revision of the process of transition to IFRS of business entities. In particular:

1.The list of persons who will prepare financial statements based on IFRS starting from the results of 2021 is mandatory. It includes joint-stock companies, commercial banks, insurance organizations and legal entities classified as large taxpayers. They will have to:

organize accounting based on IFRS from January 1, 2021;

to ensure the number of employees of accounting services sufficient for the qualitative application of international standards.

The State Assets Management Agency will annually approve and publish by June 1 the schedule for the transition of economic entities with a state share and state-owned enterprises to accounting and preparation of financial statements based on IFRS.

2. The Ministry of Finance is determined by the authorized body for the implementation of IFRS. To perform the relevant functions, a Department for coordinating the implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards and External quality control will be created in the structure of the Ministry.

Taking into account the need to train a significant number of qualified specialists with the necessary knowledge and skills, the document provides for a fundamentally new integrated approach to the training of national personnel.

The introduction of IFRS is carried out by the regulator represented by the Ministry of Finance in a phased and far-sighted manner. This does not create numerous difficulties and problems faced by States that made a choice in favor of the "big bang" with their accelerated implementation. The establishment of uniform requirements of reporting standards that affect the methodology of consolidation and accounting for joint activities, as well as the requirements for disclosure of information about the company's investments, is one of the most important stages of the process of globalization of financial reporting.

The use of financial statements prepared in accordance with the National Accounting Standards (NSB) in force in the Republic of Uzbekistan cannot fully guarantee a sufficient understanding by foreign investors of all aspects of the financial and production activities of companies in Uzbekistan.

First of all, IFRS are implemented and used by entities of public interest. Financial and credit organizations and joint-stock companies are already legally required to prepare financial statements in accordance with IFRS. Reporting in accordance with IFRS provides important financial information about the company.

Financial information is the most important tool for making economic decisions, both the possibility of attracting investments and the cost of the attracted capital for the company depends on its quality. Nowadays, information has become the most valuable resource. The advantage in the competition for financial resources will be given to those companies that will be able to provide investors with the most complete, understandable and reliable information about their financial situation.

Currently, IFRS serve this purpose much better than NSAs. One of the parts of IFRS is the accounting of investments.

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Based on the task of generating reliable information in the context of crisis phenomena, among the general problems, such problems are identified and briefly described as priority ones that are related to meeting the requirements of IFRS 3, IFRS 9, IFRS 10, IFRS 11, IFRS 12, IFRS 24, MS International Financial Reporting Standards that reflect investments and investment activities in economic entities¹.

¹ <https://fin-accounting.ru/ifrs>. IFRSs, IASs, IFRICs.[ifrs.org](http://www.ifrs.org) / Issued standards.

Fig. 1. International financial reporting Standards reflecting investments and investment activities in economic entities or (Standards regulating the formation and presentation of investment accounting)²

IFRS 3 "Business Combinations"

COMPETENCE. IFRS 3 "Business Combinations" was revised in 2008 and applies to all business combinations performed starting from July 1, 2009. There is no analogue in the national standard.

PURPOSE. The objective of IFRS 3 is to improve the relevance and comparability of the information that the company presents in its financial statements in relation to the business combination and its effects.

² Prepared by the author.

This is achieved through established principles and requirements regarding how the buyer:

- * recognizes and evaluates in its financial statements the acquired identifiable assets, assumed liabilities and non-controlling interest in the acquired company;
- * recognizes and evaluates goodwill or income generated as a result of a business combination;
- * discloses information to users of financial statements about the nature and financial effects of a business combination (Fig.).

IFRS 3 will apply to all transactions that fall under the definition of a business combination.

IFRS 3 is not applicable:

- * to create joint ventures;
- * to acquire assets or groups of assets that are not a business;
- * to merge companies under common control³.

In order to minimize the impact of these factors on the audit, it is necessary to get a very clear understanding of all the internal processes of the company and the process of consolidation itself, as well as to understand what amendments the company makes and what effect it gives. It is also necessary to understand the information system of the enterprise and the consolidation program in particular. Only after

³ACCA DipIFR Study Guide, June, 2020, prepared by the PwC Academy for the ACCA DipIFR exams in 2020. www.pwc.ru/ru/about/structure.html.

getting the full picture, it will be possible to most effectively perform an audit for the consolidated statement of financial results.

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